

1 **NLRC4 is an inhibitor of the interferon system.**

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7 The products encoded by the NOD (nucleotide oligomerization domain)-like NLR gene family function as
8 intracellular receptors of the innate immune system. We previously characterized the function of the Crohn's
9 Disease susceptibility gene *NOD2* in transcription of a wide variety of genes following pattern recognition of
10 the pathogen-associated molecular pattern (PAMP) muramyl dipeptide, the minimal biochemical component of
11 the gram negative cell wall peptidoglycan. We also described an inflammasome-type function for *NOD2*,
12 stimulating production of the inflammatory cytokine IL-1B, which mirrors the function of the canonical
13 inflammasome protein *NLRP3*, and described a major function for *NOD2* in activating the interferon system.
14 We report here that a separate member of the NLR gene family, *NLRC4*, is a broad-spectrum inhibitor of the
15 interferon system. In the human immune system, NLRs function both as powerful activators and inhibitors of
16 the interferon system.

The interferon system functions as an antiviral restriction pathway. We measured whole transcription in THP-1 monocytic cells with enforced expression of the NLR gene *NLRC4* (1). Despite activation of the stimulator of interferon response genes (*STING*), the endogenous interferon reporter gene *MX1* was repressed as a result of *NLRC4* expression. The NLR gene *NOD2* expression robustly activates *MX1* and *MX2* in human cells (2).

Figure 1: NLRC4 expression results in activation of STING, but repression of the endogenous interferon reporter gene MX1.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	[log2FoldChange]	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
340061	4.80e-117	0.1376	-22.99872	-3.1642	4121.76	STING1	687/17856	96.2
4599	9.63e-07	0.775	4.89905	3.796733	4820.22	MX1	8341/17856	53.3

Expression of genes in the human hematopoietic system that function in immune defense are controlled by the interferon regulatory transcription factors (IRFs). We measured changes in IRF expression transcriptome-wide following expression of *NLRC4* to examine the hypothesis that *NLRC4* is a broad spectrum negative regulator of interferon pathway gene expression. *IRF9*, *IRF4*, *IRF1* and *IRF2* were simultaneously silenced or significantly repressed following expression of *NLRC4* in human monocytic THP-1 cells (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Interferon regulatory factors IRF1, IRF4, IRF9 and IRF2 and are silenced by NLRC4.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	[log2FoldChange]	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
10379	3.15e-66	0.1808	17.19015	3.107791	2209.1	IRF9	1396/17856	92.2
3662	2.38e-57	0.4539	15.96134	7.244356	389.37	IRF4	1618/17856	90.9
3659	5.31e-20	0.4867	9.1575	4.457294	8991.47	IRF1	4110/17856	77.0
3660	1.91e-19	0.2703	9.0185	2.437631	2088.94	IRF2	4205/17856	76.6

The soluble interferons control expression of multiple families of genes including the interferon-inducible IFI genes and the interferon-inducible transmembrane IFITM genes whose complete set of functions and broader biological significance remain incompletely understood. We assayed control of interferon-inducible gene expression by *NLRC4* using whole transcriptome technologies and *NLRC4* over-expression (Figure 3). We observed significant silencing of the interferon-inducible gene network resulting from *NLRC4* expression in cells that recapitulate function of the human immune system (Figure 3), including the interferon alpha receptor *IFNAR1*.

Figure 3: Interferon-stimulated genes of the IFI, IFIT and IFITM families are silenced by NLRC4.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	[log2FoldChange]	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
3454	7.64e-97	0.1196	20.88304	2.497361	6848.97	IFNAR1	885/17856	95.0
3428	1.94e-90	0.1749	20.16631	3.526344	4322.67	IFI16	978/17856	94.5
402778	9.94e-34	0.3918	12.10499	4.742272	733.41	IFITM10	2728/17856	84.7
24138	6.86e-25	0.3672	10.30253	3.782684	926.08	IFIT5	3507/17856	80.4
387751	2.38e-24	0.4558	10.18221	4.641392	240.14	GVINP1	3573/17856	80.0
3434	4.76e-21	0.3124	9.41433	2.941205	542.36	IFIT1	3968/17856	77.8

1 Signals in the innate immune system are transduced from the cell membrane through intracellular
 2 intermediates of the IRAK and TRAF family, as well as TBK1. Consistent with a role for NLRC4 in negative
 3 control of the interferon system in the human immune system, we found silencing of *TBK1*, *IRAK2*, *TRAF1*,
TRAF3 and *TRAF5* as a result of NLRC4 expression in human cells (Figure 4).

4 **Figure 4: NLRC4 expression results in repression of interferon and NF- κ B intracellular signal**
 5 **transducers, including TBK1.**

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	[log2FoldChange]	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
29110	3.23e-26	0.1669	10.59256	1.767994	2776.4	TBK1	3360/17856	81.1
10010	1.13e-234	0.1023	32.7099	3.346825	5702.23	TANK	217/17856	98.8
3656	1.69e-200	0.2628	30.2112	7.938634	6177.14	IRAK2	288/17856	98.4
7185	6.59e-145	0.3795	25.63273	9.728282	12793.79	TRAF1	517/17856	97.1
7187	2.10e-95	0.113	20.72412	2.341683	5376.5	TRAF3	906/17856	94.9
7188	4.73e-74	.3018	18.2048	5.494457	641.22	TRAF5	1245/17856	93.0

10 Finally, despite activation of STING, we observed significant repression of the RNA sensor
 11 *IFIH1/MDA5* which functions in innate immune sensing of RNA and whose expression is primed by the
 12 interferon pathway (Figure 5). Together, the data demonstrate strong and broad regulation of the innate
 immune system by NLRC4. NLRC4 functions as an inhibitor of the interferon system.

13 **Figure 5: Despite activation of STING, expression of NLRC4 expression results in repression of RNA**
 14 **sensor IFIH1 (MDA5).**

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	[log2FoldChange]	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
64135	7.64e-29	0.3396	11.14419	3.784975	3895.51	IFIH1	3110/17856	74.2

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